

InsSciDE Policy Brief

Building an interdisciplinary
European science diplomacy.

InsSciDE

Inventing a shared Science
Diplomacy for Europe

Building an interdisciplinary European science diplomacy

The policies recommended in this paper stem from the values at the heart of the InsSciDE project – *Inventing a shared Science Diplomacy for Europe*.¹ InsSciDE employs a variety of research methodologies and approaches, draws from a range of disciplines, and creates an inclusive and cross-sectoral dialogue with a range of stakeholders, to:

- **generate knowledge** on past and present science diplomacy;
- **construct guidance, training, and other best practice materials** for practitioners, the EU and Member States; and, among other things, to
- **provide direction for policy** at EU and Member State levels.

Science diplomacy is at the core of work to achieve the **UN's Sustainable Development Goals**. It is by its nature **an interdisciplinary endeavour**, combining and merging together the disciplines of science and diplomacy.

In this paper, we advocate a multi- and inter-disciplinary understanding of science itself, which takes into account a **diversity of knowledge systems** within academia and society. Understanding science in this way will enable us to make the most of its **transformational power**.

Stemming from the values of the InsSciDE project, we suggest policies at the above multiple levels to promote an interdisciplinary approach to science diplomacy in Europe. Policy- and decision-makers should:

1. Governance

- Incorporate interdisciplinarity into the governing structures of scientific institutions and diplomatic academies by adjusting hiring and promotional practices to value interdisciplinary expertise and skills. Encourage interdisciplinarity in the governance of non-state actors that may be relevant for science diplomacy.

2. Research & Funding

- Design and secure innovative funding schemes through multi-institutional and intersectoral collaboration, and create specific interdisciplinary research opportunities. Increase flexibility in funding frameworks to support the interdisciplinary endeavour.
- Offer guidance and criteria for incorporating and evaluating excellence in interdisciplinarity in research.

3. Pedagogy

- Promote curricula, starting at undergraduate levels, which ensure that teaching approaches integrate knowledge from different disciplines, in this way demonstrating the impact of interdisciplinarity on the core disciplines involved.

4. Knowledge Transfer

- Foster conditions for data mobility and accessibility across disciplines to support interdisciplinary research.
- Build platforms and physical/virtual meeting places for interdisciplinary collaborative actions.

¹ This is InsSciDE's first policy brief, constructed in the early stages of the project. It is not based on InsSciDE's forthcoming empirical research.

Interdisciplinarity in the InsSciDE project

InsSciDE is a fundamentally multi- and interdisciplinary project; it brings together historians, natural scientists, political scientists, philosophers, archaeologists and experts from a variety of other disciplines to conduct interdisciplinary research. This research is carried out in direct contact with practitioners and other experts from a variety of sectors.

To take an example, InsSciDE author Prof. Maria Rentetzi's case study on 'Addressing nuclear security through the study of IAEA's safeguards system' stands "at the intersection, on the one hand, of history, philosophy and sociology of nuclear science and technology and, on the other, of international history and diplomatic studies".² InsSciDE's 23 other case studies combine disciplines such as political science, STS and archaeology.

What do we mean by interdisciplinarity when it comes to science diplomacy?

Interdisciplinarity in science diplomacy should be understood at two levels. At the first level, science diplomacy is not to be understood as the mere juxtaposition of two disciplines, but rather as the holistic interexchange of knowledge and methodologies between them.

At the second level, science diplomacy should be driven by a broad and interdisciplinary understanding of science, which covers a range of disciplines from natural sciences to engineering, to social sciences and the humanities, where these disciplines form part of a cohesive model.³

A multidisciplinary model involves drawing from a range of disciplines, whereas interdisciplinarity requires an element of combination and mergence. Understanding science diplomacy in this way, there is a wider range of actors who may be understood to be 'science diplomats'.

Why emphasise interdisciplinarity in science diplomacy research and practice?

European science diplomacy experience is by nature multifaceted, comprising a wide range of actors, histories and disciplinary backgrounds.

Collaboration between researchers from different fields, the incorporation of knowledge from a range of practitioners, and the resulting interdisciplinary perspective, can thus facilitate a more comprehensive representation of science diplomacy realities. Additionally, employing a repertoire of research methods avoids the exclusion of particular avenues of inquiry and knowledge.

Combined with this, the global context in which science diplomacy is situated demands an interdisciplinary perspective. The UN's 169 targets for achieving the SDGs highlight the need for interdisciplinary responses to global challenges. For example, environmental challenges raise questions of monitoring, multilateralism, climate change communication, and traditional knowledge.

There is thus a web of connections between science diplomacy, interdisciplinarity, and the SDGs: interdisciplinarity is embedded into both the SDGs and science diplomacy; the SDGs inform the aims of science diplomacy; and science diplomacy is essential for achieving the SDGs.

Europe's science diplomacy capital: an opportunity to consolidate and formalise

InsSciDE begins with a hypothesis: that EU Member States have a great capital of science diplomacy experience on which they can draw, but this practice is fragmented, unrecognized, or lacking an overall model that can consolidate and leverage this knowledge for Europe.⁴ This paper proposes that interdisciplinarity functions as one part of the consolidating glue that binds together Europe's science diplomacy experience and provides a shared end for European actors.

We now look ahead to the next three years for the InsSciDE project. Our case studies will provide insights into science diplomacy in areas relevant to the SDGs, targeting Health (3), Environment (13, 14, etc.), Security (cross-cutting target), and promoting peace and partnership (16, 17) through Heritage and Space. Policies that enable us to make the most of our science diplomacy capital will be essential to achieving the SDGs by

² Rentetzi, Maria (2018), *Pitch 6.4a - Addressing nuclear security through the study of IAEA's safeguards system*, available at: <http://www.insscide.eu/spip.php?article190> (Accessed: 25 January 2019)

³ Thanks to our InsSciDE colleague Dr. Rasmus Gjedssø Bertelsen (UiT) for his input on this.

⁴ European Commission (2017), *Grant Agreement No 770523*, European Commission

References

Rentetzi, Maria (2018), *Pitch 6.4a - Addressing nuclear security through the study of IAEA's safeguards system*, available at: <http://www.insscide.eu/spip.php?article190> (Accessed: 30 January 2019).

European Commission (2017), Grant Agreement N° 770523, European Commission.

